

CURRENT SCIENCE

Depression In The Elderly

“Everyone wants to live long; but nobody wants to grow old.” (“Seminar on “Towards a Silver Lining for Golden Years” held in city”)

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To cite this article Anita ÖSME, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 3, 2023, p. 27 – 56. - 0099-0001-2301-0502.

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ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

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journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

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Abstract

Aging is a developmental process that is unavoidable for all living things and carries with it a loss in a wide variety of functions. This is because aging is a developmental process. Eric Erikson, an American psychologist who was active in the field of developmental psychology and made significant contributions to the field throughout his lifetime (1902-1994), saw human development as a process that occurs across an individual's whole life. The eighth and last step of this process is called "ego integration or despair," and it is the conclusion of this process. This phase encompasses the latter years of life. At this time, the individual will either

CURRENT SCIENCE

come to terms with all that has happened to him during his life and feel contentment as a result of the accomplishments he has achieved, or he may spiral into depression and believe that his life has been pointless and empty. The fear of passing away is accompanied by the thought that there is no hope. Old age is a period that is experienced differently by each individual in ways that are relative to them. The meaning that a person ascribes to old age is developed as a result of all of these ideas, feelings, and experiences from their history. The sensation of despair is exacerbated by previous failures, objectives that are impossible to achieve, emotions of worthlessness and uselessness, and diminished social interactions and cognitive skills. As a consequence, the individual is left feeling quite depressed. In the event that the circumstance deteriorates further, they will be unable to get out of bed, and they may refuse to eat or drink. The elderly often go through a few different kinds of psychological shifts as they become older. These shifts have either a favorable or a detrimental impact on the entirety of an aged person's life, including the personal, familial, social, and health-related facets. Depression is one of the most common mental illnesses that people face in their later years. Depression, which is rather frequent among older people, continues to be a significant health concern in old age due to the fact that it lowers one's quality of life and raises the cost of medical care. As the signs and symptoms of depression, which is widespread in the old, are different, it might be regarded as a normal result of aging, which is something that patients' families and physicians frequently do not identify in their patients. Depression is common in the elderly. In addition, there is a wide range of responses to various treatments. As a consequence of this, depression in older people is one of the conditions that is hardest to diagnose and is frequently treated in an insufficient manner. While depression is often present in the initial stages of dementia in the elderly, it is imperative that this factor be taken into consideration when making a diagnosis of dementia.

The idea of pseudodementia, which is often confused with depression, will also be covered in this research. This will come after a brief introduction to the concept of aging in general, which will be followed by an examination of depression and its causes, both of which are common in elderly people. Pseudodementia and depression are often confused with one another.

Keywords: *Old age, Aging, Depression, Pseudodementia*

Introduction

CURRENT SCIENCE

As an extension of maturity, old age is described as a period in which both physical and mental changes are visible in the latter era of life. This occurs in the later years of a person's life. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines aging as a reduction in one's capacity to adjust one's behavior in response to changes in their surroundings. The notion of aging may refer to a variety of various aspects depending on the live object being discussed. However, when discussing human aging, in addition to these processes, psychological, social, societal, and cultural meanings are also attributed to aging. Aging is primarily related to biological and physiological processes in non-human organisms; however, when discussing human aging, these meanings are also attributed to aging.

Depression is one of the most prevalent forms of mental illness that can affect people of advanced age. When dealing with older patients, prompt therapy is essential in the event that depression is appropriately diagnosed. As a consequence of this, it will be feasible to accomplish a significant improvement or rise in the level of quality of life enjoyed by the aged. On the other hand, the old person's life might be jeopardized in unfavorable ways if the therapy is either postponed or not received at all.

One of the factors that can lead to depression in the elderly is when their children get married and move out, when they become single, especially after the death of a spouse, when they retire (which can result in a loss of status as well as monetary loss), when they have to move into a nursing home or nursing home, when they have health problems, and when there are disruptions in the activities of daily living.

Because the process of aging can have an impact on one's cognitive abilities as well as their physiological systems, it is not always easy to spot signs of depression. As a result of the natural process of aging, new health issues may arise; hence, the diagnosis and treatment of depression should be approached with extra care and attention.

1. The Concept Of Age

Beginning at infancy and continuing through maturity and into old age, development is an ongoing process. Changes that take place in a person's body during the course of their lifetime can have an effect on the person's attitudes, cognitive processes, and actions. Alterations can also be seen in the nature of the challenges that individuals must surmount during the course of their life (Atkinson & Hilgard , 1995).

CURRENT SCIENCE

Eric Erikson's theory of psychosocial development includes eight stages, with old age being the eighth and final stage. There are eight crucial stages in life, according to Erikson's theory, and each stage contains two characteristics that are diametrically opposed to one another. It is anticipated that the person will, at some point throughout each phase, triumph over these two conflicting aspects of the crisis. The capacity to weather these storms is a prerequisite for achieving success and contentment in life. In addition, there is a relationship that may be made between the stages. Specifically, if the individual can successfully overcome the challenge that he is currently facing, he will be able to move on to the next stage in a manner that is better prepared for it. The eighth and final stage is known as "despair against self-integrity," and it is the stage that occurs in conjunction with old age. When an older person is self-integrated, they have good sentiments and views about their own life. On the other hand, when an older person is despairing, which is the opposing aspect, they might be hopeless, belligerent, and even fear death (Bilgin, Tamkoc, Aydoğdu, 2021).

Table 1. Erikson's Stages of Psychosocial Development

STAGES	AGES
Basic Confidence x Distrust	0-1
Autonomy x Shame	2-3
Attempt x Guilt	4-5
Work x Feelings of Inferiority	6-12
Identity x Role Confusion	12-18
Intimacy x Solitude	20
Productivity x Stability	Adulthood
Self Integrity x Despair	Senile

The method in which one confronts their own mortality is at the heart of Erikson's ultimate psychological crisis, which he refers to as wholeness-despair. The golden years are a period for introspection and a review of one's life's experiences up until that point (Atkinson & Hilgard , 1995).

According to Akdemir and Ozdemir (2006), senility is a notion that considers biological, social, economic, and temporal factors. Old age is a term that, when used as a definition for the word, represents the late stages of life, also known as the last phases. During this time, the individual

CURRENT SCIENCE

will go through a series of changes that will primarily consist of losses and collapses in many aspects of their lives. Around this period, the elderly is most likely to experience a loss of physical function. Yet, there are also losses on the social, economic, cultural, psychological, and cognitive fronts, in addition to these losses on the physical front. According to Onat and Çevik (2006), all these losses are truly normal losses that may be encountered in a person as they become older. The process of becoming older is a normal part of life. Just as natural developmental phases such as childhood, adolescence, and maturity are experienced beginning at birth, the time of old age can be experienced in the same manner. Old age, like other stages of life, is a period that has its own progression and set of qualities to look out for. At this time, one's physical and mental power will both be on the decline. In addition, the idea of old age is a relative one, which means that it differs from person to person, society to society, and culture to culture.

The process that we refer to as aging is not an illness but rather a gradual decline in the overall productivity of the body. The process of aging refers to the gradual accumulation of structural and functional alterations in anatomical and physiological dimensions that can take place independently of trauma, illness, or disease and are dependent on the passage of time. According to Ayn (2004), the term "aging" is most often used to refer to changes in a biological system.

It is vital to have a clear definition of and accurate perception of certain aspects to arrive at an accurate assessment of aging and the challenges that come with advanced age. These points are able to be formulated in the form of three primary questions:

- a) *What does it mean to be of Old Age?*
- b) *Can you define health for me?*
- c) *What kind of connections may be made between age and one's state of health? (Bilir, 2006).*

The chronological idea of age refers to the amount of time that has passed since a person's birth. On the other hand, according to the World Health Organization's (WHO) definition, health is "the individual's physical, mental, and social well-being." [Citation needed] During their lives, individuals are exposed to a wide range of environmental influences. The human body goes through a series of changes because of being exposed to these elements. Alterations in the organism's structure and function take place throughout time, and these alterations, together with external influences, have a significant impact in determining how well a person can maintain their health. These adjustments do not have a detrimental impact on the individual,

CURRENT SCIENCE

and as a result, they do not compromise the person's state of health in any way. The term "physiological alterations" refers to this situation, which occurs when changes occur at a level that is normal. However, the fact that elderly people have a greater number of health problems than younger people give the appearance that old age and diseases go hand in hand. Additionally, this impression contributes to the belief that elderly people are fond of one another and that old age and health problems go hand in hand. Yet, even though a higher prevalence of illnesses is associated with advancing age, it is not accurate to assume that all older individuals are afflicted with illness and are consequently unhappy. In the same vein, it is possible to assert that the belief that illnesses are an inevitable consequence of becoming older is not accurate (Bilir, 2006). "Who is the more experienced one?" (Cangoz, 2006) suggests that a topic that is intricately connected to this one is "What constitutes natural aging?" The term "normal aging" refers to the physiological, biochemical, and functional changes that occur in all organs of aged people. Importantly, these changes are not the result of any illness or state of health; rather, they are merely the result of a natural progression of development, or the progression of time (Amuk and Ozhanoglu, 2003). This is the most crucial point to take away from this. Actually, "who is the older?" The responses to the question lead to a variety of interpretations on what it means to be an adult. These:

Aging as a function of time: According to Cangaz, 2006, this is a phrase that refers to the year that has passed since a person was born, but it does not give any information regarding how or why changes associated to aging occur. Chronological age is the primary factor that determines life durations in civilizations. For instance, the age range of 50 to 65 is regarded to be advanced maturity, but the age range of 65 and more is considered to be old age (Akin, 2006).

Biological aging is a term that refers to the unfavorable changes that take place in the structure and physiology of the body throughout the course of an individual's lifetime. These changes take place in a manner that is progressive, accumulative, and exacerbates with time. According to Akin (2006), the indicators of biological aging include the development of wrinkles in the skin, a reduction in muscular strength, a loss of eyesight and hearing, and a slowing of the rate at which the heart beats.

According to Amuk and Ozhanoglu (2003), the term "psychological aging" refers to the process through which the old experience shifts in their behavioral, adaptive, cognitive, and personality functions as a direct result of their increasing age. It is possible for old people to have feelings of yearning for the past, difficulty to break away from the past, worry for the future, insecurity, and anxiety depending on how far along in age they are. And as a direct

CURRENT SCIENCE

consequence of this, a more sensitive and sensitive personality structure may be found in those who are older (Akin, 2006).

The process through which the function that an individual play in society shifts as they become older is referred to as social aging. For instance, an individual may quit the group at work due to circumstances such as retirement. According to Akin (2006), the fact that he is unable to participate in social activities to an adequate degree has a detrimental impact on his health.

Pathological Aging: Pathological aging can be brought on by ingrained cultural practices or external environmental elements. For instance, pathological aging can be caused by an excessive consumption of protein-containing foods because of dietary habits; an insufficient consumption of vegetable and fruit foods; excessive and inadequate nutrition as a result of financial ignorance; and disorders in the organ systems of the body (Akin, 2006).

Economic Aging: As a result of the change in financial conditions due to retirement and leaving the job, the change in the lifestyle of the senior person, as well as the loss in financial prospects, place the elderly in a difficult financial situation (Akin, 2006).

The entire aging series is comprised of the individual processes of chronological aging, biological aging, psychological aging, social aging, pathogenic aging, and economic aging. According to Akin (2006), the process of aging takes place as a consequence of the interaction between all of these different series. According to demographic standards, the age of 65 is considered to be the beginning of old age. The age range from 65 to 74 years old is considered to be "young old" by the World Health Organization (WHO), whereas the age range from 75 to 84 years old is considered to be "middle-aged" and "older old" respectively (85 and over).

In 2017, the World Health Organization (WHO) established that the definition of an elder is older than 65 years old, which is also known as an advanced age. To be more specific, those aged 0 to 17 fall into the category of "adolescent," those aged 18 to 65 fall into the category of "young," those aged 66 to 79 fall into the category of "middle age," and those aged 80 and more fall into the category of "old" (Bilir, 2018). During historical events, B.C. Homer, who lived in the eighth century B.C., is credited with originating the notion of old age, which has related to a life spent in paradise since that time. Plato, who lived between the years 424 and 347 B.C., was 81 years old when he died. According to Plato, the process of aging is unique to everyone, and the best way to get ready for it is to ensure that all your responsibilities during your youth and adulthood are completely satisfied. Sophocles, who lived to be 89 years old, believed that the knowledge, experience, and advice of older people should be given the necessary attention

CURRENT SCIENCE

and importance (Onat and Çevik, 2006). Sophocles believed that the old man was a wise person, and that necessary attention and importance should be given to the knowledge, experience, and advice of older people. The French physician Jean-Martin Charcot is credited with conducting the very first investigations on the treatment of elderly patients and the aging process in the year 1881.

Although the first studies on the aging process focused on the body and the spirit, the first regulation issued by the World Health Organization added the social dimension to these dimensions and drew attention to the common issues faced by elderly people in conjunction with the rise in the number of elderly people following the Second World War. According to Onat and Çevik (2006), the establishment of the ideas of "geriatrics" and "gerontology" occurred at the beginning of the 20th century because of the growing number of issues experienced by aged people and the increased attention paid to this condition by everyone. The field of medicine that deals with the diagnosis and treatment of diseases seen in elderly individuals in the aging process, that is, the field of medicine at the old age process, is called "geriatric" (Aydın, 2004). The term "gerontology" refers to the branch of science that studies the aging process in all its biological, physiological, psychological, cognitive, sociological, and economic aspects. For an individual to successfully complete the process of psychosocial development, there are certain developmental tasks that must be completed during each era of development. The following are the primary responsibilities that come with old age:

- *Adapting to retirement and declining earnings*
- *Establishing a direct relationship with the age group*
- *Establishing joyful living conditions*
- *Adapting to declines in physical strength and health*
- *Adapting to the death of relatives, spouse*
- *Fulfilling social and civic duties (Aydın, 2004).*

2. Depression In The Elderly

The assumption that some of the psychological changes experienced in the elderly are due to their age, that is, old age, is one that nearly everyone makes at some point in their lives. For instance, if an older person is cranky, obstinate, or melancholy... well, just about every trait

CURRENT SCIENCE

conceivable is thought to be the most distinguishing characteristic of the elderly. An individual's age may be linked to a wide range of good and bad emotions as well as actions; in other words, "he" is experiencing this sensation and thinking since he is an older person. On the other hand, as time goes on and people become older, they experience a series of changes in their bodies as well. It is believed that some medical ailments with inadequate explanations are caused not only by the physical challenges of elderly individuals but also by their mental health issues. Although if at least some of the mental problems that are seen in elderly people have a physical explanation, this explanation is deceptive since the majority of the psychopathology that is seen in elderly people is not attributable to the physiological aging processes that take place in their bodies. Personality qualities that are incompatible with one another in old age and a lack of suitable coping skills play a key part in the development of psychiatric problems, as well as in health, hereditary orientation, and the causes of stress in life (Davison & Neale, 2004).

Depression is one of the most prevalent forms of mental disease that affects people who are 65 and older. Depression is recognized as a serious public health issue owing to the fact that it considerably diminishes the quality of life of elderly people and contributes to an increase in expenditures within the health sector. It is common for patients' families and physicians to miss the diagnosis of senile depression because the signs and symptoms of depression in old age are distinct from those of depression in younger age, and since old age is regarded as a natural symptom of aging. Because of this, depression that occurs in the elderly is one of the most difficult disorders that cannot be treated adequately because it is difficult to recognize and has a wide variety of treatment options. As a result of this, depression that occurs in the elderly is one of the most difficult disorders that can be treated adequately. Yet, depression may also be considered as a cause of suicide, and the diagnosis and treatment of depression is a highly significant and specialized field, particularly at this elderly age. Suicide can also be seen as a result of depression.

Depression in the elderly may be confused with somatic complaints and cognitive symptoms, or the elderly may have trouble expressing their anguish, sorrow, and mood changes. Alternatively, somatic complaints and cognitive symptoms may be confused with depression in the elderly. The prevalence of major depressive disorder and/or depression symptoms is significant among senior adults who are hospitalized for physical sickness or who are residing in nursing homes (Cankurtaran, 2006).

2.1 Symptoms of Depression in the Elderly

Depression is very common in old age, as in other age groups. Although this situation significantly reduces the quality of life of people, it can cause serious negativities. During depression, many factors such as biological, psychological, personal, sociological, economic and cognitive in the elderly are significantly affected. Depression in the elderly may show a different distribution of symptoms compared to those in other age groups. The symptoms of depression in the elderly are as follows (Iscen , 2006):

- *Depressed mood such as sadness, grief, anguish*
- *Changes in personality and behavior, problems (agitation, aggressive, irritable, touchy, sensitive, intolerance)*
- *Decreased energy, strength, slowing of psychomotor functions, regression*
- *Decreased self-care, such as refusing to take medication , not seeing a doctor*
- *concentrating , focusing, attention*
- *Change in appetite and weight (increase or decrease)*
- *Change (increase or decrease) in sleep time*
- *Increased unexplained bodily pains and complaints (somatic preoccupations)*
- *Frequency of going to the doctor/hospital*
- *not enjoying life*
- *feeling worthless*
- *Losing the ability to cope with loss*
- *Forgetfulness (memory problems)*
- *Thoughts of death and related suicidal thoughts (Kaya, 1999)*

Table 2. DSM-V Depression Diagnostic Criteria (*Büyükgök and Kulaksızoğlu, 2021*)

Major Depression Symptom Checklist
1. Depressed mood is present for most of the day, nearly every day, and is either self-reported (e.g., sad, feeling empty or hopeless) or observed by others (e.g. looks tearful).

CURRENT SCIENCE

2. A marked decrease in interest or pleasure in all or nearly all activities is present most of the day, nearly every day (as determined by subjective expression or observation).
3. Losing or gaining a lot of weight when not trying to lose weight (not dieting) (eg , a change of more than 5% of body weight in a month) or a decrease or increase in cravings almost every day.
4. Insomnia or oversleeping nearly every day.
5. almost daily, psychomotor provoking (agitation) or slowing down (observable by others, not merely as subjective, inability to calm down or have a sense of slowing down).
6. Fatigue or lack of inner strength (low energy) nearly every day.
7. Feelings of worthlessness or excessive or inappropriate guilt (which can be delusional) nearly every day. (“Depression: Screening and Diagnosis AAFP”)
8. Difficulty thinking or concentrating, or indecisiveness nearly every day (subjectively described or observed by others).
9. Recurrent thoughts of death (not just fear of death), recurrent thoughts of suicide (suicide) without planning a specific action, or attempting to kill oneself or planning a specific action to kill oneself.
Ongoing (Dysthymia) Depression Disorder Symptom Checklist
1. Decreased appetite or overeating.
2. Insomnia or excessive sleepiness.
3. Decreased energy level or exhaustion.
4. Decreased self-esteem.
5. Difficulty focusing or making decisions.
6. Feelings of hopelessness.

According to the diagnostic criteria for depression listed above that were established by the American Psychiatric Association with the DSM-V, at least five of the depressive symptoms must have been present during the two-week period, and at least one of these symptoms must be either a depressed mood or a loss of interest or pleasure. The aged can have clinically substantial discomfort or a deterioration in functional areas (work-related, social, etc.) as a result of these symptoms.

2.2 Causes of Depression in the Elderly

CURRENT SCIENCE

The etiology of depression in the elderly can be traced back to a wide variety of causes. Women are more likely than males to suffer from depression as they become older. Physical diseases, multiple drug use, and nutritional deficiency all play a role in the normal aging process as well as diseases in which some biochemical changes belonging to the pathological aging process affect depression and greatly affect body systems. These factors all play a role in the etiology of depression in the elderly. In old age, in addition to the physical problems that might be noticed, cognitive impairments can also be visible. Because of the enormous impact that these physical and cognitive impairments have on depression in the elderly, it can be challenging to diagnose and treat depression in this population. It has been hypothesized that environmental aspects might potentially play a role in the development of depression. Among these environmental factors are a decrease in social relations/social isolation, a decrease in the capacity for intimacy, low self-esteem, a low socioeconomic level, the loss of a spouse, retirement, being a woman, being single, being divorced, factors that cause stress, the presence of medical and neurological diseases, and the use of drugs, alcohol, and other substances. There are psychological and social risk factors, such as living in a nursing home/nursing home, having had a previous episode of depression, having attempted suicide in the past, having cognitive impairment (problems in mental abilities such as memory and attention), loss of loved ones, and recent negative life events (Davison & Neale, 2004; Ozaşkinli, Ozturk, Eraslan & Bora, 2005; Kaya, 1999).

Table 3. *Factors Affecting the Progression of Depression in the Elderly (İşcen , 2006)*

Negative Factors	Positive Factors
limited life	good functionality
lack of hobby	to have occupations
physical illness	Regular health checkup
lack of activity	Being socially active

CURRENT SCIENCE

malnutrition	regular diet
mild dementia	good vision, good cognitive level
Don't lose your spouse	living with spouse
Social Isolation	Good family ties
Economic troubles	Good income level
Housing and maintenance problem	familiar environment

2.3 Dementia Against Dementia (Pseudodementia)

Depression in older individuals can lead to a condition known as pseudodementia, which is characterized by a decline in cognitive abilities such as attention, memory, and the ability to conceptualize. When older people who exhibit evidence of dementia receive therapy for their depression, several research studies have found that these patients enjoy alleviation or improvement in their depression. On the other hand, due to the frequent identification of cognitive impairment in patients who suffer from depression, instances of depression are commonly misinterpreted as dementia. This is a significant problem for differential diagnosis since, unlike dementia, depression can typically be treated, but dementia cannot be treated.

It might be challenging to tell the difference between real dementia and cognitive impairment that is caused by depression. If forgetfulness and other dementia symptoms started before the symptoms of depression; if dementia symptoms have not changed with depression treatment; if dementia symptoms persist after depression treatment; if the patient is not aware of his cognitive loss - if he has no insight into his loss - then it should be considered in favor of dementia. When a patient has cognitive impairment because of depression, they are reluctant to do a cognitive evaluation, can act indifferent, are aware of their cognitive losses, and report a more specific and recent history of when their cognitive losses began. People who suffer from

CURRENT SCIENCE

depression may exhibit amnesia, which may lead their loved ones to assume dementia. Yet, those who suffer from depression may complain of forgetfulness, whereas persons with dementia forget what they forgot to complain about (Eker, 1998; Bayraktar, 1997; Cankurtaran, 2006).

Table 4. *Some Clinical Differences Between Dementia and Pseudodementia (Sivrioğlu and Kırılı, 2001; Çakmak and Saatçioğlu, 2003)*

Clinical Appearance	pseudodementia	dementia
Start format	Fast and outgoing with behavior change	Insidious and progressing over months
mood	apathetic or depressed	Fluctuating, sometimes apathetic , sometimes normal
cognitive loss	severely complained about	Complain is rare
distant memory	Equal and sudden deterioration	Worse recent memory
remembering specific events	not remembered	Equally forgettable as other events
attention and concentration	usually good	usually bad
Nighttime exacerbation of symptoms	None	There is
intellectual functions	He has a lot of complaints, he complains about not being able to do the tests, but the results are good in objective tests.	Neuropsychological tests are not objective, patients feel inadequate
sense of self	Weak	Normal
Findings related to his condition	Anxiety, insomnia, anorexia	Rare: sometimes insomnia

CURRENT SCIENCE

Duration	Variable, symptoms may disappear spontaneously or with treatment	Symptoms progress slowly over months or years
Reason for application	They apply themselves, they are worried about dementia, they have received information about dementia	The patient is brought by the relatives of the patient who notice changes in memory, personality or behavior.
Story	Psychiatric history and/or familial/personal problems	Family history of dementia is not uncommon

2.4 Differences and Difficulties in the Diagnosis of Depression in the Elderly

Depression is a condition that, in older people, is frequently misdiagnosed (since it is considered to be a normal result of being older) or cannot be treated well, even when it is recognized as present. The senior population presents certain diagnostic challenges when it comes to depression. The following is a list of the reasons that are contributing to these difficulties:

- 1. The elderly cannot fully name the mood changes (such as hopelessness, fear), and some complaints, sleep and appetite changes are seen in the elderly, and these are defined as a normal medical illness, not depression. 1. There are differences in the clinical manifestation of depression in the elderly. 2. The elderly cannot fully name the mood changes (such as hopelessness, fear).*
- 2. People who are elderly take their mental health issues, such as feelings of hopelessness, worthlessness, and suicidal thoughts, personally and experience shame. They have difficulty expressing these issues because they are afraid that other people will stigmatize them, and they also put off going to the doctor because of this fear.*
- 3. Dementia and other forms of cognitive impairment are also common in older people as they age. As a direct consequence of this, older people could have trouble comprehending and communicating their current mental state.*
- 4. Society has erroneous views and prejudices about older people, which contribute to its perception of depression in this population. Nonetheless, just*

CURRENT SCIENCE

like with people of other age groups, it is common and even to be anticipated for older people to suffer from depression.

- 5. Doctors may also be biased and mistakenly believe that the feelings of despair that are common in older people are just a normal part of being older. As a direct result of this, treatment is delayed, which can occasionally result in extremely dangerous repercussions, including death.*

It is clear that depression in senior people can develop with a wide variety of clinical problems, depending on the factors that were discussed previously. It is important to keep in mind that both the diagnosis and treatment of depression can be challenging. If a patient expresses any signs of sadness, especially suicidal thoughts or physical discomfort, it will be helpful for the doctor to get some rest and begin the necessary therapy right away. It is important to keep in mind that sadness is not a normal consequence of getting older as people become older (Aki , 2013).

2.5 Consequences of Depression in the Elderly

The changes that have been noted in the old person (by his family and the person or individuals he is responsible for), the issues that have been voiced or sought to be explained by the elderly person, should be taken into consideration as soon as possible, and a doctor should be called. The physician needs to pay close attention to all of the patient's concerns before arriving at an accurate diagnosis and initiating therapy. Because senior depression makes the treatment process harder and more time consuming than it is for persons of other age groups, elderly depression is one of the reasons why. In the event that therapy for depression yields either favorable or negative effects, it is imperative that treatment be initiated and meticulously monitored. In the event that this does not occur, there is the potential for life-threatening repercussions. In this regard, the following is a list of some of the implications that depression can have on older people:

- A decrease or worsening in the aged person's entire functionality, including personal, social, and vocational facets of life.*
- A decline in one's quality of life as well as overall degradation.*

CURRENT SCIENCE

- *The possibility of committing suicide, which in turn brings about a greater danger of dying.*
- *Decreased cognitive function, which is associated with an increased risk of acquiring dementia.*
- *An rise in the number of times medical services are used, which drives up the cost of such treatments.*
- *Exhaustion among people who provide care for senior citizens (family, caregiver, caregivers if they stay in the institution, etc.).*
- *A decline in people's overall health and an increase in the number of cases of various illnesses.*
- *Excessive levels of anxiety and substance addiction.*

2.6 Scales Used to Evaluate Depression in the Elderly

2.6.1 Geriatric Depression Scale

Features of the Scale:

- *Original Name: Geriatric Depression scale .*
- *Those aged 60 and older who do not suffer from moderate or severe dementia and who do not have major hearing issues are included in the applicable and target group.*
- *Qualification Assessed: The purpose of this study was to assess the amount and severity of depressive symptoms in older adults by evaluating them in terms of depression.*
- *Type of Scale: The scale is set up in such a way that individuals can mark it on their own. On the other hand, taking into account the levels of education, health, and social activity of the old people, it would be suitable for the interviewer to read the items on the scale and note the replies obtained by the interviewer.*
- *Scope: The scale has a total of thirty items, and respondents are asked to select either "Yes" or "No" as the appropriate response to each question.*

CURRENT SCIENCE

- *Instructions on how to use the scale are written down and located at the beginning of the scale. It is sufficient to mark the 30 items given as Yes/No on the sentences you were given. In instances where it is not possible for it to be filled by itself, the interviewer will read the questions aloud and mark the responses. If the elder is unsure of the answer to a question, the interviewer will read the question to him again, and if more explanation is required, they will supply it before giving him the opportunity to respond. When it is at all practicable, every effort is made to ensure that there are no blank items.*
- *Instructions: The instructions for the scale are given at the beginning of the process, and throughout the interview with the individual, it is discussed which criteria will be used to determine the final score.*
- *The final score was 1. 5. 7. 9. 15. 19. 21. 28. 29. 30. The number 0 represents a yes answer to a question, whereas the number 1 represents a no answer. In some of the other questions, the coding goes in the opposite manner; yes, responses are given a value of 1, while no answers are given a value of 0. The possible range for the total score is from 0 to 30.*
- *Evaluation: 0-14 moderate depression; 14-30 serious depression (Koroğlu & Aydemir, 2012).*

Table 5. Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS)

Please answer the following questions about how you felt in the last week of your life by ticking the appropriate answer for you.

	YES	NO
1) Are you basically satisfied with your life?		
2) Do you still pursue most of your personal activities and interests?		

CURRENT SCIENCE

3) Do you feel your life is empty?		
4) Are you often bored?		
5) Are you hopeless about the future?		
6) Do you ever feel uncomfortable because of the thoughts you can't get out of your head?		
7) Are you generally in a good mood?		
8) Are you afraid that something bad will happen to you?		
9) Do you feel happy most of the time?		
10) Do you often feel helpless?		
11) Are you often restless and restless?		
12) Would you rather stay at home than go out and do something new?		
13) Do you often worry about the future?		
14) Do you feel that your memory is weaker than most?		
15) Do you think it is a beautiful thing to be alive right now?		
16) Do you often feel sad and sad?		
17) Do you feel worthless as you are now?		
18) Do you worry a lot about the past?		
19) Do you find life enjoyable and exciting?		

20) Is it difficult for you to start new projects?		
21) Do you feel full of energy?		
22) Do you think you are in an unresolved situation?		
23) Do you think most people are better off than you?		
24) Do you often get upset over small things?		
25) Do you often feel like crying?		
26) Do you have difficulty concentrating?		
27) Do you like to start your day in the morning?		
28) Do you avoid attending social gatherings?		
29) Is it easy for you to make a decision?		
30) Is your mind as clear as it used to be?		

2.6.2 Cornell Depression Scale for Dementia

Features of the Scale:

- *Original Name: Cornell Scale for Depression in Dementia .*
- *Applicable / Target Group: Dementia sufferers.*
- *The scale improves the detection of depressive symptoms in individuals with dementia in accordance with the information acquired from the patient and the caregiver.*
- *The interviewer is the one who makes the determinations regarding this type of scale.*

CURRENT SCIENCE

- The total number of elements on the scale is 19, and it is broken down into five distinct categories.
- Application: The information needed to fill out the scale can be obtained from the patient's family as well as their caretakers.
- These are the instructions: A total of 19 things on the scale will be questioned, and a score between 0 and 2 points will be assigned to each one based on how severe it is.
- The grading system assigns a value between 0-1-2 to each item on the scale, depending on how difficult the questions were. 0= none; 1= mild or moderate; 3 = severe.
- Throughout the evaluation, the severity is indicated by the overall score. According to Koroğlu and Aydemir (2012), a score that is lower than six points shows the lack of depressive symptoms.

Table 6. Cornell Depression Scale in Dementia (CDS)

A. Mood-related findings			
1. Anxiety (Restless look, brooding look, anxious state)	0	one	2
2. Sadness (sad face, sad tone, tearful mood)	0	one	2
3. Not reacting to joyful events	0	one	2
4. Irritability (Easily anger, short-term relaxation)	0	one	2
B. Behavior changes			
5. Agitation (Uneasy body language, clasping hands, pulling hair)	0	one	2
6. Retardation (slowed movement, slow speech, slowed reaction)	0	one	2
7. Multiple physical complaints (0 points if only gastrointestinal complaints)	0	one	2
8. Loss of interest (Decreased interest in usual activities)	0	one	2
C. physical findings			
9. Loss of appetite (Eating less than usual)	0	one	2
10. Weight loss (2 points if more than 2.5 kg lost in 1 month)	0	one	2
11. Loss of energy (fatigue easily, inability to maintain activity)	0	one	2
D. Cyclic functions			

CURRENT SCIENCE

12. Diurnal change in mood (Symptoms are worse in the morning)	0	one	2
13. Difficulty falling asleep (falling asleep later than usual)	0	one	2
14. Frequent waking from sleep	0	one	2
15. Waking up early in the morning (Waking up earlier than usual)	0	one	2
E. intellectual changes			
16. Suicide (not finding life worth living, suicidal ideation or attempt)	0	one	2
17. Poor self-confidence (self-blame, worthlessness, feeling of failure/incompetence)	0	one	2
18. Pessimism (Expectation of Evil)	0	one	2
19. Delusions consistent with mood (delusions of poverty, illness, loss)	0	one	2

2.7 Treatment of Depression in the Elderly

When depression is identified in older adults, treatment should begin right away just as it would at any other time in a person's life. In a multidisciplinary setting, it is essential to employ a therapy that draws from a variety of fields, including pharmaceutical, psychological, and sociological approaches. The provision of all the physical, psychological, and social requirements of the older people who are depressed should be the primary focus here. Antidepressants, psychotherapy interviews, and ECT (electroconvulsive therapy) are all effective treatments for depression in adults, and they can also be used successfully with older patients. There is a subtype of depression known as psychotic depression that can occur in conjunction with depressive symptoms. If this is the case, it is recommended that antipsychotic medication be used in addition to antidepressant medication over the course of treatment. With this particular instance of psychotic depression, however, there is a possibility of life-threatening complications, such as suicide ideation. In this scenario, senior citizens need to be kept under constant surveillance and should immediately begin receiving follow-up care as well as the required therapy. It is essential to make use of ECT (electroconvulsive therapy) in this case, and a favorable response can be achieved through treatment by a physician who specializes in this field. During this time period, it will be possible to observe more beneficial benefits from the treatment if the family engages in it on a regular basis. It is important to

CURRENT SCIENCE

provide the family and the older person with all of the necessary information on depression, as well as to explain the treatment plan, its aim, and its approach. In addition, engaging in physically demanding pursuits during this time might be of some benefit. Positive improvements and advantages may be noted in the life and general functionality of the senior depressed individual, particularly when taking short walks, getting out of the surroundings, and engaging in social contexts. This is especially true when the individual goes outside. In addition, various medical conditions that are common in the elderly should not be overlooked, particularly at this time, and treatments that are essential should be maintained (Eren, 2020; Aki, 2013).

2.8 Evaluation of Depression in the Elderly

1. *An in-depth and in-depth history should be gathered from the senior patient as well as their family. This history should include the commencement of the disease, its progress, the patient's general medical history, as well as current and former medications.*
2. *An evaluation of the patient's mental health, including the presence or absence of a depressed state and cognitive functions, should be carried out.*
3. *It is recommended to do a standard mental state evaluation, which includes standardized mini-mental testing and more in-depth neuropsychological testing if it is deemed essential.*
4. *It is recommended to undertake a comprehensive physical examination; any medical or neurological conditions should be ruled out.*
5. *Appropriate blood and urine tests are to be sought, including blood and urine tests, levels of vitamin B12 and folate, RPR/VDRL, HIV testing, urine drug screening, and brain imaging investigations.*
6. *It is imperative that all current medical conditions be handled, which includes the discontinuation of any unsuitable medications and the initiation of any essential treatment (such as medication, psychotherapy, etc). (Eren, 2020).*

2.9 Approaching a Depressed Elderly Person

- *To begin, it is essential that people understand and keep in mind that depression may affect people of any age, even the elderly, and that it can occur at any point*

CURRENT SCIENCE

in one's life. The elderly is in chronic physical and psychological complaints, which can put you in a depressed condition and put you at a greater risk for developing depression. Yet, the symptoms of depression in an elderly individual may be different from those in other age groups. Pay close attention and have a calm demeanor. Approach without passing judgment, with understanding, and with a willingness to make sacrifices for yourself. • When an elderly person seeks medical attention or is brought to a physician by a member of their family, the physician should ensure that the patient is well rested. After the necessary examinations and examinations have been performed and a diagnosis of depression has been made, the elderly patient should be followed up on, and the procedure that will be followed should be explained to both the patient and his family. Because depression in older people is a prolonged process and an illness that requires care from both the elderly and their families, it is important that depression be taken seriously. Together with the help of a psychiatrist and a psychologist, participation in this therapy process is equally essential (these two specialists are experts in the field of geriatrics, which will shape the treatment better).

- *A depressed older person may feel a decline in his or her sense of self-worth, which is another way of saying that their self-esteem may suffer. He is able to argue against any and all forms of collaboration and cooperation. In this particular scenario, you should make an effort to boost the old person's sense of self-worth by demonstrating that he is cherished and that his existence is acknowledged. Do not lose sight of the fact that the depressive state is the driving force behind the decision to reject you.*
- *Do not disregard the unhappy elderly man himself or the circumstances in which he lives, such as telling him, "you have nothing, and it's all because of old age, after some time has passed." On the other hand, you should comprehend it, be descriptive by saying things like "yes, you can feel these things, we can experience the same feelings sometimes, these indicate that we are in a little bit of mental distress, but you will get better," and you should be optimistic, sincere, and empathetic in a way that the older person can comprehend.*

CURRENT SCIENCE

- *Immediately alert the doctor and use extreme caution if the senior citizen makes it abundantly plain that he does not wish to live any longer or expresses this as a thinking.*
- *Throughout this period, there may likely be instances when he does not want to move from his bed or his room. It's best not to ignore it and just see what happens. Create opportunities for them to go outside, walks can be made inside the house and then outside, exercise programs can be organized, and activities such as chatting and drinking tea and coffee in different places can be organized to prevent the elderly from staying in their room all the time. These are some of the ways that you can prevent the elderly from staying in their room all the time.*
- *At this time, he can choose not to eat or drink anything. Confront him in an acceptable manner and tell him that to be well and healthy, he has to consume food and adequate water. Notify the attending physician as soon as possible if the test findings are negative. • Considering that there may be cognitive losses in this process, it may be useful to distract his attention with something to prevent this loss and to save him from the negative mood caused by his depression. This is because metabolic disorders can occur in the elderly because of hunger and insufficient fluid intake. Finding activities (such as knitting, solving puzzles, backgammon, and playing cards) that he can engage in as much as possible may help him become more active and vibrant. (Karagoz, 2012).*
- *Older people who are sad may wish to talk at long about their problems, feelings, and experiences. If this is the case, it is crucial to listen to them with patience and convey the sense that what they have to say is significant to the conversation. Some may find that simply relaxing is enough to help them relax. It's possible that the investment of care, love, compassion, and patience will prove to be far more effective than any medication in this process. Throughout this procedure, elderly people who are sad should not be coerced into doing anything against their will. It is important to make the necessary proposals, but one should not insist on them. Sincerity in communication with him is required if he is in a precarious circumstance.*
- *The senior population suffering from depression should have their way of thinking reorganized. It is important to encourage people to talk about their*

CURRENT SCIENCE

emotions and opinions. It is necessary to bring to one's attention the fact that there are also favorable aspects to life. Discuss the activities that he used to take pleasure in undertaking.

- *Depression may contribute to a reduction in the older person's sense of trustworthiness. Because of this, the elderly are given the opportunity to have a sense of trust, and it is made certain that they experience a reduction in emotions of hopelessness, helplessness, dread, and worry towards the future.*
- *If the elderly depressed person stays in the institution, it is essential that the caregivers (nurses, elderly care staff, doctors, psychologists, etc.) have a thorough understanding of all the processes associated with aging and that they have received at least some education in this field. This is the case even if the education was on the most fundamental level. Because the time of old age is a period with its own process that is distinct from other periods. And currently, it is even more essential for the caregivers to be more sensitive, meticulous, attentive, self-sacrificing, and true, just as it is for all old persons and particularly for an elderly person who is sad. This mental condition will be easier to overcome for the senior if he has the sense that he is treasured and protected by those around him.*
- *The negative mental state that the elderly experience should be realistically accepted and supported, and it should be explained that many of the losses (physical, psychological, social, cognitive, etc.) that can be seen in the elderly are the characteristics of old age. This explanation should be given so that the negative mental state that the elderly experience can be supported. According to Ekşioğlu (2012), an elderly person who can embrace this phase of his life together with his emotions and ideas would experience greater levels of calm, happiness, and safety.*

3. Conclusion

Within the scope of this research, we attempted to examine the relationship between advancing age and depression, which is one of the most prevalent mental diseases seen in older adults. Aging is a stage of development that comes with its own set of traits and a unique process. If this time and all of its characteristics (physical, medical, psychological, social, etc.)

CURRENT SCIENCE

are known, the process will progress more effectively and healthily for both the aged person and the person or people who care for them. Nevertheless, sadly, in our culture, "diseases that occur in old age" are still viewed as the normal outcome of becoming older, and unpleasant negative effects are seen because of this perception. To put it another way, there is a common misperception that the elderly are predisposed to a wide variety of illnesses, conditions, and changes just due to the fact that they are getting older. As a result of this erroneous view, however, terrible outcomes such as mortality might occur. Although depression is a serious mental illness, the signs and complaints of sadness, particularly those that are encountered in older people, can be quite distinct. Because of this, the family or caregiver(s) of the old person should be aware of this period and the changes that may take place, and they should make an appointment with a doctor as soon as possible. In particular with regard to the mental health of the elderly, it is advantageous for the physician who is consulted to possess both expertise and experience in the field. The reason for this is that senile depression is a serious illness that requires intensive treatment and can only be administered by a medical professional. Because depression in the elderly might either be the outcome of another underlying condition or cause another disease, the doctor should perform a thorough examination on the depressed old patient. For instance, depression can impair cognitive abilities in the old, leading to conditions such as dementia; alternatively, the elderly may already have dementia and have developed depression as a side effect of the dementia. The most crucial steps in this process include compiling a thorough patient history based on the signs and symptoms being presented by the individual in question, doing the necessary diagnostic tests, and arriving at a conclusion. In the event that a valid diagnosis of depression is arrived at, the older person who is depressed need to be treated by an expert team (physician, psychologist, etc.) and continuously monitored over the course of treatment. At this part of the conversation, the ailment of the elderly person and the treatment procedure should also be discussed to the family of the elderly person or to the persons who care for him (his caregiver if he is at home, all professional staff if he stays in the institution). Depression in older people is an illness that must be handled in all of its dimensions, requiring care, attention, and experience, as well as therapy and follow-up care. In addition, these things need to be addressed. Because of this, the formation of a geriatric unit and a geriatric team, particularly at health institutions, and as a consequence of the examination, diagnosis, and treatment, will bring about a process that is healthier and more useful.

Old age is not a disease; It is a continuation of human life with its changes, diseases, in short, with all its aspects.

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